

DataREACH

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

The goal of Project DataREACH is to make a positive impact on medicine in developing nations through data science/artificial intelligence. Through partnering with medical professionals, government officials, and public health experts in Cameroon via Songhai Labs, Project DataREACH has signed an agreement with HSPC Polyclinic in Kumba Cameroon to develop the very first clinician integrated pipeline for machine learning based risk assessment of noninfectious diseases in Cameroon and among the first on the African continent. Project DataREACH is partnering with the Cameroon Ministry of Health in order to implement a smart medical surveillance platform for district level outbreak detection and multivariate time series analysis for diseases spread predictions. DataREACH Labs is private research and development lab at the intersection of artificial intelligence and the life sciences.

Author biography

Vikash Singh Founder/CEO of DataREACH

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